

Supplementary Table 1: Attributes of localities and samples. See data appendix for data type by individual sample.

ATTRIBUTES OF SAMPLES AND LOCALITIES

Locality	Region	Data type	Stratigraphic range of OAE2 interval (m)	Number of preBZ samples	Number of BZ samples	Number of postBZ samples	Stratigraphic range of BZ samples (m)	Preservation of samples
Bull Creek	Northern	Ordinal and continuous	0-30 (this study)	15.00	15.00	3.00	30-45 (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)	Fair (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)
Black Gap	Northern	Ordinal and continuous	4-15 (this study)	12.00	8.00	0.00	22-30 (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)	Fair (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)
Hot Springs	Northern	Ordinal and continuous	1-18 (this study)	12.00	4.00	14.00	30-34 (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)	Fair (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)
Horesetooth Reservoir	Central	Ordinal	18-23 (this study)	0.00	4.00	6.00	17-20 (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)	Poor (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)
Rock Canyon	Central	Ordinal and continuous	20-35 (Caron et al. 2006)	3.00	6.00	21.00	20-25 (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)	Fair (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)
Cuba	Central	continuous	200-475 (Bowman and Bralower 2005)	5.00	5.00	51.00	210-250 (Elderbak et al. 2014)	Moderate to poor (Elderbak et al. 2014)
Bunker Hill	Central	Ordinal and continuous	2-17 (this study)	0.00	3.00	12.00	8-10 (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)	Fair (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)
Hartland-Bridge Creek	Central	Ordinal and continuous	18-28 (this study)	5.00	3.00	33.00	17-19 (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)	Fair (Eicher and Worstell, 1970)
Lozier Canyon	Southern	continuous	28-39 (Lowery et al. 2014)	5.00	11.00	28.00	28.5-36.1 (Lowery et al. 2014)	Moderate to poor (Lowery et al. 2014; Lowery and Leckie, 2017)
Carthage	Southern	continuous	9-28 (Bryant et al. 2021)	10.00	8.00	17.00	11-14.6 (Bryant et al. 2021)	Moderate (Bryant et al. 2021)

Supplementary Table 3: Spearman correlations between PCO axis scores and the percent abundance of calcareous benthic foraminifera for each sample. sp=species-level PCO analysis. mp=morphotype-level PCO analysis. * = p<0.05; *** = p<0.001.

CORRELATION BETWEEN PCO SCORES AND %CALCAREOUS

Axis	Spearman rho
PCO1sp	0.5***
PCO2sp	-0.13*
PCO1mp	0.39***
PCO2mp	-0.41***

Supplementary Table 4: Significance test results between PCO scores of BZ and nonBZ samples by locality. * = p<0.05; ** = p<0.01, *** = p<0.001

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN BZ AND NONBZ SAMPLES WITHIN A LOCALITY

Region	Locality	PCO1sp	PCO2sp	PCO1mp	PCO2mp
Northern	BC	U = 61**	U = 203*	U = 142	U = 50**
Northern	BG	U = 69	U = 29	U = 47	U = 43
Northern	HS	U = 32	U = 37	U = 24	U = 23
Central	HR	U = 11	U = 16	U = 16	U = 16
Central	RC	U = 27*	U = 56	U = 39	U = 18*
Central	HBC	U = 21	U = 111**	U = 41	U = 37
Central	BH	U = 2*	U = 34*	U = 5	U = 19
Central	CK	U = 28**	U = 165	U = 55*	U = 117
Southern	LC	U = 178	U = 89*	U = 180.5	U = 107.5*
Southern	CNM	U = 102	U = 132	U = 133	U = 178**

Supplementary Table 6: Significance test results of PCO scores of BZ samples between individual localities and of PCO scores of nonBZ samples between localities. Blue = northern region; Green = central region; orange = southern region. * = p<0.05; ** = p<0.01, *** = p<0.001

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO1sp BZ samples									
Black Gap	U = 0***								
Hot Springs	U = 7*	U = 26							
Horsetooth Reservoir	U = 4**	U = 29*	U = 10						
Rock Canyon	U = 11**	U = 40*	U = 12	U = 10					
Hartland-Bridge Creek	U = 7	U = 23*	U = 9	U = 8	U = 12				
Bunker Hill	U = 17	U = 24*	U = 11	U = 10	U = 15	U = 8			
Cuba	U = 19	U = 39**	U = 16	U = 16	U = 21	U = 9	U = 4		
Lozier Canyon	U = 0***	U = 52	U = 11	U = 1**	U = 5**	U = 0**	U = 0**	U = 0***	
Carthage	U = 16**	U = 54*	U = 18	U = 13	U = 24	U = 7	U = 4	U = 10	U = 77**

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO1sp nonBZ samples									
Black Gap	U = 32**								
Hot Springs	U = 37.5***	U = 124							
Horsetooth Reservoir	U = 2***	U = 37.5	U = 93.5						
Rock Canyon	U = 0***	U = 97	U = 296.5	U = 33*					
Hartland-Bridge Creek	U = 42***	U = 156	U = 440	U = 75	U = 454.5				
Bunker Hill	U = 18***	U = 51	U = 157	U = 20	U = 150	U = 255			
Cuba	U = 64***	U = 203*	U = 591	U = 90	U = 564	U = 959.5	U = 269		
Lozier Canyon	U = 0***	U = 116.5*	U = 424.5	U = 39.5*	U = 420	U = 659	U = 173	U = 1096	
Carthage	U = 120**	U = 173	U = 476.5*	U = 76	U = 494**	U = 728.5**	U = 203	U = 1169***	U = 700***

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO1mp BZ samples									
Black Gap	U = 4***								
Hot Springs	U = 6*	U = 29*							
Horsetooth Reservoir	U = 24	U = 32**	U = 15						
Rock Canyon	U = 19*	U = 41*	U = 12	U = 5					
Hartland-Bridge Creek	U = 7	U = 20	U = 6	U = 2	U = 6				
Bunker Hill	U = 14	U = 24*	U = 12	U = 5	U = 13	U = 8			
Cuba	U = 28	U = 38**	U = 17	U = 9	U = 20	U = 13	U = 9		
Lozier Canyon	U = 4***	U = 48	U = 7	U = 0**	U = 8*	U = 5	U = 0**	U = 1***	
Carthage	U = 8***	U = 29	U = 8	U = 2*	U = 7*	U = 4	U = 2	U = 3*	U = 34

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO1mp nonBZ samples									
Black Gap	U = 36**								
Hot Springs	U = 45.5***	U = 138							
Horsetooth Reservoir	U = 61	U = 56	U = 127*						
Rock Canyon	U = 42***	U = 141.5	U = 358	U = 28*					
Hartland-Bridge Creek	U = 127***	U = 213	U = 510	U = 53*	U = 423				
Bunker Hill	U = 16***	U = 73.5	U = 190	U = 15	U = 151.5	U = 253			
Cuba	U = 167***	U = 294	U = 712	U = 64.5**	U = 563	U = 995.5	U = 282.5		
Lozier Canyon	U = 62***	U = 206	U = 519	U = 37.5*	U = 434	U = 686	U = 169	U = 1101	
Carthage	U = 36***	U = 178	U = 430	U = 29*	U = 374	U = 576	U = 126	U = 921.5	U = 517

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO2sp BZ samples									
BG	U = 87								
HS	U = 39	U = 22							
HR	U = 47	U = 21	U = 8						
RC	U = 56	U = 31	U = 12	U = 11					
HBC	U = 15	U = 0*	U = 3	U = 0	U = 6				
BH	U = 15	U = 1*	U = 2	U = 0	U = 3	U = 3			
CK	U = 50	U = 15*	U = 6	U = 5	U = 11	U = 15*	U = 15*		
LC	U = 129*	U = 62	U = 18	U = 18	U = 28	U = 33**	U = 33**	U = 46*	
CNM	U = 66	U = 14	U = 7	U = 5	U = 14	U = 21	U = 19	U = 14	U = 8**

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO2sp nonBZ samples									
BG	U = 94								
HS	U = 270.5	U = 189							
HR	U = 90*	U = 63.5*	U = 125.5*						
RC	U = 286	U = 207*	U = 385.5	U = 34					
HBC	U = 385	U = 273	U = 495	U = 61	U = 390.5				
BH	U = 137	U = 102	U = 179	U = 18	U = 160	U = 247			
CK	U = 659	U = 398	U = 670	U = 75*	U = 530	U = 988.5	U = 263		
LC	U = 390	U = 296.5*	U = 522.5	U = 45.5*	U = 393	U = 693	U = 145	U = 1039	
CNM	U = 242	U = 190	U = 342.5	U = 34*	U = 291	U = 432.5	U = 104	U = 656	U = 423

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO2mp BZ samples									
BG	U = 77								
HS	U = 45	U = 27							
HR	U = 35	U = 15	U = 5						
RC	U = 70	U = 42*	U = 13	U = 16					
HBC	U = 34	U = 21	U = 7	U = 8	U = 7				
BH	U = 35	U = 21	U = 8	U = 9	U = 9	U = 6			
CK	U = 52	U = 29	U = 7	U = 11	U = 7	U = 5	U = 2		
LC	U = 116	U = 59	U = 16	U = 26	U = 17	U = 10	U = 7	U = 29	
CNM	U = 74	U = 24	U = 2*	U = 15	U = 2**	U = 0*	U = 0*	U = 8	U = 15*

	BC	BG	HS	HR	RC	HBC	BH	CK	LC
PCO2mp nonBZ samples									
BG	U = 203***								
HS	U = 423.5***	U = 134							
HR	U = 104***	U = 47	U = 104						
RC	U = 381***	U = 131.5	U = 338	U = 44					
HBC	U = 637***	U = 263	U = 614	U = 101	U = 532				
BH	U = 211***	U = 100.5	U = 223*	U = 43	U = 198.5	U = 280			
CK	U = 937***	U = 376	U = 879	U = 139.5	U = 732	U = 1013.5	U = 253.5		
LC	U = 586***	U = 228	U = 673*	U = 72.5	U = 541*	U = 625	U = 143	U = 1007	
CNM	U = 484***	U = 229*	U = 531**	U = 76	U = 529***	U = 637	U = 142	U = 1017.5**	U = 644**